

Invisible Peace Architectures: Rethinking Early Warning Systems through Galtung's Conflict Triangle in Kenya's Sondu Border Conflict

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ABSTRACT: This paper explores the efficacy of Early Warning and Early Response (EWER) mechanisms in recurring conflicts along intra-state borders via the case of the Sondu border between the Kenyan counties of Kisumu and Kericho. From a theoretical perspective based on the conflict triangle of Johan Galtung, the paper argues that formal early warning and response measures have remained constrained as they are preoccupied only with violent forms of conflict, and do not engage with the structural and cultural processes of reproduction of conflict sufficiently. Adopting an instrumental mixed methods approach, using qualitative research techniques predominantly, data were gathered via Key Informant Interviews, Focus Group Discussions, questionnaires, verbal histories, and documentary analysis from members of the community, administrators, conflict resolution practitioners, and civil society groups. The main result of the research is that there is a huge discrepancy: while communities are aware of the role of the actors in their local informal conflict resolution efforts including chiefs, elders, churches, and civil society organizations, they have little knowledge of the institutional early warning framework known as CEWARN. In addition, rumour-mongering, political mobilization, distrust, and past grievances may often serve as indicators of upcoming violence in advance of formal warning procedures.

KEYWORDS: Early Warning Systems; Hybrid Peace Infrastructures; Peacebuilding; Conflict Prevention; Kenya; Sondu Border; Community Perceptions; Legitimacy

1.0. INTRODUCTION

Perhaps one of the most significant paradigmatic changes in peace and conflict studies today concerns the shift from conflict management to preventive peacebuilding (Galtung, 1976; Lund, 2009; Ramsbotham, Woodhouse, & Miall, 2011). Earlier efforts towards managing violent conflicts involved primarily peacekeeping operations, military stabilization, ceasefire agreements, mediations after escalation, and post-conflict reconstruction (Boutros-Ghali, 1992; Bercovitch & Jackson, 2009; Wallensteen, 2015). But the intellectual tradition that Galtung began fundamentally shifted this narrow conception of conflict, arguing that violence and conflict should not only be understood after becoming manifest but also before. For Galtung (1964, 1976, 1990), violence cannot be limited to physical confrontation; rather, it comprises three distinct dimensions - direct, structural, and cultural - which together constitute conflict dynamics and produce it repeatedly. This means that prevention entails far more than reacting quickly to clashes, raids, killing, or displacement. Prevention requires also understanding the less visible social, political, economic, and symbolic conditions through which violence is constructed, legitimized, naturalized, and expected. Hence, Galtung's Conflict Triangle is still one of the most illuminating frameworks for asking about the real preventive value of early warning systems that tend to focus on direct violence and thus react after structural and cultural tensions have reached open confrontation.

Early Warning and Early Response (EWER) system can be discussed in the context of the broader trend towards prevention mentioned above. As Wulf and Debiel (2009) describe, the evolution of early warning started from military intelligence and humanitarian crisis monitoring to become a political and peacebuilding instrument of anticipating potential threats and acting preventively. In a similar vein, according to Austin (2004), as cited in Wulf and Debiel (2009), early warning can be understood as a comprehensive process that includes data gathering and analysis, risk assessment, recommendations, and information sharing among relevant parties. According to Woocher (2008), also cited in Wulf and Debiel (2009), early warning presupposes risk estimation, threat analysis, and sharing warning information with decision-makers. Thus, the concepts above underlie the institutional design of EWER systems at the global, regional, and national level of peace architectures. Nevertheless, Wulf and

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Debiel (2009) raise an issue of crucial importance for the analysis of early warning systems in Africa – namely, who receives a warning and how this warning is acted upon?

This issue has great analytical significance in the context of African peace and security governance and its gradual institutionalization of early warning systems at continental, regional, and national levels. First of all, both Continental Early Warning System of the African Union and CEWARN (African Union, 2020; IGAD, 2012) demonstrate institutionalization of the notion that conflicts are predictable and can be avoided through systematic data gathering and analysis combined with coordinated response. Second, the Kenya's National Policy on Peacebuilding and Conflict Management (2015) shows a clear preventive approach to conflict through formalizing conflict prevention and response as one of the major pillars and building the national and sub-national peace infrastructures to integrate state officials, peace committees, civil society organizations, and other relevant parties. Design-wise, Kenya's EWER system is clearly in line with the global and regional preventive turn. Nevertheless, the persistence of recurrent internal border conflicts gives rise to a different question, namely whether EWER systems can detect and respond to both direct violence and structural/cultural aspects of conflict identified by Galtung.

Peace Studies literature provides some answers to the question but does not exhaust the debate. First, there is literature on the potential and design of early warning systems that emphasizes their ability to collect, analyze, and act based on relevant information (Matveeva, 2006; Wulf & Debiel, 2009). Second, there is literature on local peace infrastructure and peace networks that demonstrates that peacebuilding is never solely the affair of the state but relies on the involvement of civil society, religious actors, elders, peace committees, and other informal authorities (Ernstorfer, 2018; Kut, 2007; Odalo, Okoth, & Were, 2022). Third, there is critical literature on peacebuilding interventions that argues that peace architectures may become institutionally detached from the reality of life and thus be perceived as thin and externally oriented (Cravo, 2018). Clearly, each of these strands speaks to another and complements existing insights, but not comprehensively enough. While early warning literature tends to focus on systems and processes, infrastructure of peace literature tends to focus on actors and networks, while critical literature focuses on the legitimacy of peacebuilding interventions. What remains unexplored to a considerable extent is a Galtungian view of how EWER systems relate to structural and cultural aspects of conflict and violence experienced by communities before direct confrontation occurs.

Indeed, this gap is evident within the body of research produced within Kenya regarding internal conflict. Studies that focus on the borderlands between Kisumu and Kericho as well as other conflict zones highlight the role of ethnicity, election-related violence, cattle rustling, land disputes, and inter-community competition as key themes (Juma & Simiyu, 2019; Kamau, 2020; KECOSCE, 2022; NCIC, 2023; Ombeck, Okoth, & Matanga, 2019; Saferworld, 2015). These studies are relevant since they outline key conflict actors, incidents, and triggers. However, there is a tendency to gloss over whether the formal early warning architecture of the country has sufficient capability to address conflict in terms of detection. In particular, these studies fail to consider whether EWER can detect behavioural expressions of violence only, such as raids, fighting, hate speech, and politically-motivated violence, or if they go beyond to also capture the cultural conditions under which violence arises and perpetuates. That is the space into which this study aims to venture. Rather than asking about the existence of early warning systems, it seeks to assess whether early warning systems are socially capable of detecting conflict.

The Sondu corridor, located between Kisumu and Kericho counties, represents a pertinent case for this analysis. The area in question represents much more than a mere site of conflict. On the one hand, Sondu features communities sharing similar markets, language contacts, intermarriages, mutual food exchange, and economic interdependence while, on the other hand, they suffer from recurrent tension arising out of factors like land dispute, cattle rustling, politics, ethnic mistrust, border disputes, and disrupted markets (Kaburu, 2022; NCIC, 2022; Ojalah, 2021). As such, River Sondu forms the physical boundary between the Luos and the Kipsigis while Sondu Market symbolizes the economic and social space where collaboration and conflict are continuously engaged in. Sondu represents an interesting case study because it highlights not only the interdependence, but also conflict potential of a certain community. According to Galtungian approach to conflict, Sondu is thus more than direct violence.

Justification for studying Sondu is also found in the available empirical information. Saferworld (2015) classifies the interface between Kisumu-Kericho/Nyakach-Nandi as one of the main interfaces of conflict within Kisumu County. Similarly, the borderland of Sondu and other areas represent areas of recurring inter-ethnic tension according to Juma and Simiyu (2019). In addition, recent policy reports reveal clashes within the Kericho-Kisumu border that resulted in casualties, injuries, displacement, looting, destruction of property, and insecurity (ACLED, 2023; NCIC, 2023). In addition, the thesis background identifies several conflicts, including Pokomo-Orma, Moyale, Marsabit, Samburu, Baringo, Laikipia-Isiolo, and Meru-Isiolo as some of the most prominent border conflicts in Kenya, with NCIC reporting that 33 out of 47 counties in Kenya are involved in conflict over land and border issues (Elfversson, 2019; IPSTC, 2013; KNCHR, 2012; NCIC, 2018, 2024). However, Sondu represents a unique case in terms of its distinctiveness from other conflicts along the borderland. Unlike the aforementioned cases, Sondu is easily accessible, densely populated, fertile, commercialized, politically and economically integrated, and reachable by state institutions.

For all the above reasons, this article employs the case of Sondu as instrumental for reconsidering EWER efficiency from the perspective of Galtungian Conflict Triangle. Specifically, this paper seeks to show that despite the obvious existence of early

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warning systems within Kenya, their efficacy remains rather low due to the inability to identify the structural and cultural conditions underlying the manifestation of direct conflict and violence. Warning signs, such as rumors, youth mobilizations, cattle rustlings, political incitements, ethnic mistrust, fears of market disruption, and declining interpersonal trust, can be clearly observed before the eruption of actual violent behavior in Sondu. Thus, the analytical challenge posed here revolves around the issue of low conversion rate of socially available warnings into preventive action.

2.0. LITERATURE REVIEW

The scholarly field of EWER systems has grown substantially within peace and conflict studies, especially after the post-Cold War period of preventive peacebuilding across the globe. Most of this literature has been premised on the basic idea that violent conflicts do not arise out of thin air but develop through identifiable trends of tension, institutional weaknesses, social grievances, political mobilization, and deterioration in inter-group relations, which can be monitored in advance and prevented (Lund, 2009; Matveeva, 2006; Wulf & Debiel, 2009). Accordingly, EWER systems became tools for collecting, analyzing, and communicating information about potential risks of conflict to actors who can initiate preventative measures (Austin, 2004; Woocher, 2008). The effectiveness of these EWER mechanisms has been attributed to factors such as accurate information gathering, timely information analysis, coordinated action, and rapid preventive reactions before conflicts turn violent (Nyheim, 2009; Schmeidl & Jenkins, 1998). While the systems-oriented literature offers substantial insights into the functioning of EWER mechanisms, it tends to neglect the social and political processes through which conflicts emerge and escalate.

This problem has attracted increased criticism from critical scholars in recent years, who have argued that EWER systems often fail not because of the lack of information but due to the filtering of warning knowledge through politics, disconnection from society, and neglect in institutional practice (Wulf & Debiel, 2009; Cravo, 2018). Communities living in conflict-prone areas are likely to know about the impending conflicts well before formal institutions begin to monitor them. Signs of rising tensions may include rumours, fears, changes in the market, political instigation, youth mobilizations, and weakening of inter-group relations. However, institutional warning systems tend to prioritize measurable incidents and security threats over socially embedded warning knowledge, thus creating an interpretative gap between warning systems and the experiences of insecurity within communities. Critical scholars such as Richmond (2011) and Mac Ginty (2014), in line with the general tradition of critical peacebuilding, highlight the tendency for peace infrastructures to become formal governance mechanisms detached from the actual experiences of peace within communities. As a result, formal peace infrastructures may appear institutionally present yet socially absent.

Another relevant body of literature emphasizes the role of local infrastructures of peace in community-based peacebuilding. Studies carried out by Odalo, Okoth, and Were (2022); Ernstorfer (2018); and Kut (2007) show that peace infrastructures often involve hybrid networks of community elders, religious figures, women, youth, civil societies, chiefs, local peace committees, and other local actors who have contextual legitimacy and access unavailable to state institutions. Local actors are especially significant in the cases of African conflicts since they actively produce and maintain peace through dialogue, reciprocity, customary laws, and local dispute resolution mechanisms. This literature is valuable because it extends our understanding of peace infrastructures beyond state actors. However, this literature may sometimes idealize "the local" without engaging critically with the possibility that local infrastructures of peace could reproduce exclusion, ethnic prejudice, patriarchal oppression, and informal inequalities. Moreover, there is a relative scarcity of studies dedicated to analyzing the interaction between formal EWER systems and the local infrastructure of peace, especially in cases of recurrent internal border conflicts.

In the African context of peace and security governance, the EWER systems are increasingly being institutionalized within continental and regional organizations. The African Union's CEWS and IGAD's CEWARN are the products of the continent's broader interest in preventive peacebuilding and conflict prevention (African Union, 2020; IGAD, 2012). They rely on the assumption that the proper collection of warning information and a rapid institutional response could prevent violent escalations. Existing literature recognizes the significance of such regional institutions for improving the capacity of conflict monitoring in Horn of Africa and East Africa (Van der Lijn, 2011; Wepundi, 2011). At the same time, however, existing literature highlights various difficulties associated with such EWER systems, which include lack of political will, weak state cooperation, poor local integration, inadequate resources, and slow response implementation. Practically speaking, information on conflicts alone cannot guarantee appropriate actions since bureaucratization, political interests, distrust, and fragmented coordination may impede the efforts even when warnings are clear (Wulf & Debiel, 2009). Such a situation indicates that the challenge faced by EWER systems lies not just in their technical ability to gather information but in the broader political and institutional context.

Similar progress has been made within the scholarship on Kenyan conflict prevention, especially with regard to electoral, cattle, ethnic, and land-related conflicts. Research conducted in conflict-prone borderlands of Kisumu-Kericho, Baringo, Laikipia, Marsabit, and northern regions highlights the repetitive nature of conflicts driven by factors such as political instigation, resource competition, ethnic polarization, historical animosity, territorial disputes, unemployment, and lack of state legitimacy (Juma & Simiyu, 2019; KECOSCE, 2022; Saferworld, 2015). In addition, the Kenyan government's adoption of a National Policy on

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Peacebuilding and Conflict Management institutionalized the preventive approach, introducing national and subnational peace infrastructures to promote conflict prevention, mediation, and response (Government of Kenya, 2015). Nonetheless, as demonstrated by many empirical studies, internal conflicts in Kenya tend to remain cyclical despite the existence of peace infrastructures. Existing research is largely centered on the events, actors, and triggers of conflict, giving less attention to the question of whether Kenya's EWER systems can detect the deeper causes of conflict before violence erupts. Thus, much of Kenyan literature is event-focused and preoccupied with violence.

Here, Galtung's concept of conflict triangle becomes crucial for analytical purposes. According to Galtung (1969, 1976, 1990), there are three types of violence – direct, structural, and cultural. Direct violence involves physical harms such as killing, clashes, displacement, and destruction. Structural violence includes inequalities, exclusion, marginalization, and institutional arrangements that put certain groups at a disadvantage. Finally, cultural violence consists of beliefs, narratives, memories, and ideologies that normalize hostility and exclusion. What sets Galtung's framework apart is his insistence that violence is not only a set of direct incidents but also a set of invisible structural and cultural conditions through which violence becomes possible and socially sustained. In relation to the question of EWER systems, this idea poses the problem of whether such systems are capable of detecting the deeper aspects of violence or whether they focus only on preventing direct violence after its emergence. This issue receives relatively little attention in existing EWER literature, thus generating an important gap in the field.

Sondu presents a good case for addressing this gap. Existing studies and reports suggest that Sondu is an area defined by ethnic tensions, political competition, market disruption, cattle theft, and recurrent violence (NCIC, 2022, 2023; Ojalah, 2021; Saferworld, 2015). However, this area is also known for its trade relations, shared markets, marital history, and daily interactions between the two communities of Luo and Kipsigis. Sondu becomes interesting for analysis precisely because of this combination of cooperation and conflict, demonstrating that conflict-prone areas cannot be reduced to instances of violence alone. Rather, they are socially constructed environments characterized by continuous negotiation of issues related to trust, fear, suspicion, and politicization. Although much has been written about conflict incidents in the area, the problem of whether Kenya's EWER system engages with socially embedded dimensions of conflict has received little attention. Thus, the present study attempts to contribute to the literature by discussing whether the EWER system of Kenya recognizes the structural and cultural aspects of conflicts before escalating into direct violence. The analytical framework is presented in Figure 2 below.

3.0. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research employed the mixed-methods research methodology, with qualitative dominance, in the examination of the effectiveness of EWER systems in the context of recurrent Sondu border conflict in Kenya between Kisumu and Kericho counties. The choice of the methodological approach was dictated by the very nature of the research problem being explored. Not only did the study attempt to determine whether EWER structures exist institutionally, but also to understand how these are experienced, interpreted, trusted, operated and contested by the local community in the conflict-prone borderlands. The set of the questions that relate to warning signs, conflict narratives, trust, institutional presence, political involvement, local participation and response effectiveness required interpretive skills alongside with descriptive patterns. According to Creswell and Poth (2016), mixed-methods research may be considered appropriate if researchers attempt to combine numerical trends with the deeper contextual understanding in order to interpret some complex social phenomenon in question. Therefore, the current study involved a combination of qualitative and quantitative methodologies with qualitative methodology remaining dominant.

For the purpose of the research, the qualitatively dominant mixed-methods instrumental case study design was used. As was stated above, instrumental case study approach is suitable for examining cases that facilitate a greater understanding of a specific problem from the perspective of a larger theory or policy agenda. According to Stake (1995), instrumental case studies allow researchers to investigate a particular problem or issue that is exemplified by certain specific cases. Similarly, Yin (2018) argues that a case study approach is particularly relevant when researchers study some current phenomena in real-world setting with the help of various forms of data. Sondu became such a case since its recurrence of inter-communal violence, political sensitivity, cross-border interactions, and the existence of formal and informal peace structures make it particularly interesting for a detailed examination of EWER systems functioning. In addition, this case study allows exploring how warning signs emerge, get transmitted and lead to a proper response in a socially complex borderland environment.

Qualitative approach was the dominant research methodology in the current study due to the fact that the research problem concerned the nature of warning perception among conflict parties, the role of trust in communication channels of warning, the interactions between formal and informal mechanisms of conflict management, and reasons for warning inefficiency at the early stages of conflict escalation. Creswell and Creswell (2018) observe that qualitative research is useful for studying how individuals construct meaning within natural settings. Thus, the social construction of conflict warning and response in Sondu could hardly be studied without a qualitative approach since the borderland environment is shaped not only by violence but also by rumors, mistrust, political rhetoric, ethnic perceptions, historical grievances, and informal mechanisms of conflict resolution that cannot be adequately

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described using numbers. However, it should be noted that a supportive quantitative approach provided descriptive patterns in the form of frequency distributions and statistics on levels of awareness, trust, participation, warning practice, training exposure, and EWER effectiveness.

The study was carried out in the Sondu border corridor, which is located along the boundary between Kisumu and Kericho counties in western Kenya. It was purposively selected because it represents the conflict zone marked by the recurrent intra-state conflicts between ethnic groups associated with periodic inter-communal violence, livestock theft, political mobilization, market disruption and insecurity (NCIC, 2022, 2023; Saferworld, 2015). However, the chosen area also demonstrates high dependence between Luo and Kipsigis communities in terms of trading, transportation, market visits, intermarriage and everyday social contact, thus making it a good case for examining both conflict and coexistence simultaneously. The target population for the research comprised local residents, youth leaders, traders, elders, religious leaders, chiefs, NGAOs, representatives of civil society, members of local peace committees, and county-level peace actors active within the Sondu borderland.

The total number of 370 respondents selected for the survey represents a representative sample of the broader Sondu conflict area. The sample size was calculated using Yamane's (1967) formula for the large population size with an additional non-response factor considered during fieldwork planning. For the purpose of the study, respondents were selected based on the principle of purposive and systematic selection in order to cover conflict-affected social categories residing within the Sondu borderland. The primary task of the quantitative component of the research was to generate descriptive patterns of community attitudes towards EWER systems in terms of awareness, warning and conflict reporting practice, trust, participation in conflict management processes, CEWARN effectiveness, training received and problems affecting EWER operation.

The qualitative research relied on purposive sampling technique since the information-rich participants capable of providing insights into conflict dynamics and peace-building activities within the selected area were required. Data collection took place between November 2025 and April 2026. In order to achieve the goal of data triangulation, the qualitative component comprised 35 Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) and 8 Focus Group Discussions (FGDs). KIIs involved chiefs, assistant county commissioners, NGAOs, religious leaders, civil society representatives, elders, youth leaders, county peace actors, and other local administrators who are directly engaged in the process of managing and responding to conflict situations. In turn, FGDs consisted of youth, traders, women, elders, and common residents from Sondu borderland. Such a combination of participants was needed because experiences of warning perception, trust, and confidence in institutions may differ among people from different social categories and ethnic backgrounds.

The current study employed various data collection techniques in order to ensure triangulation and collect multifaceted information about the problem under investigation. Specifically, primary data were collected using the following methods: structured questionnaires, KIIs, FGDs, verbal histories, and field observations. Questionnaire-based data allowed collecting quantitative data on awareness, trust, participation, warning timeliness, and the effectiveness of conflict management system. Information-rich interviews and FGDs produced qualitative data related to the issues of institutional legitimacy, political interference, rumours, warning practices, lack of coordination, historical tensions, and conflict experiences. Verbal history was used for tracing how communities recall previous conflicts and their outcomes in terms of retaliatory acts, displacement of people, violence, and reconciliation attempts. Secondary data were collected in the form of documentary analysis, which involved the study of various policy documents, government publications, conflict assessments, peace-building frameworks, academic literature, NGO reports, and CEWARN-related literature.

The analysis of quantitative data was performed descriptively. In this respect, frequencies and percentage distributions were used in order to trace patterns concerning awareness, participation, trust, conflict warning practices, reporting behaviors, and perceived effectiveness of conflict resolution mechanisms. In contrast to a traditional quantitative research, in the current study, statistical generalizations were not used because the goal was to complement and deepen the qualitative findings through the use of descriptive measures. On the contrary, a thematic content analysis was applied in relation to the qualitative data collected. Thus, interview data, discussion results, oral histories, and field observations were coded with respect to the emerging topics and themes. Some of the most salient themes were as follows: institutional presence, trust, warning timeliness, participation, political involvement, structural violence, cultural violence, and coordination problems. Moreover, coding was done both inductively by looking at the data and participants' narratives and deductively through applying the concept of Galtung's conflict triangle to analyze the data.

Validity, reliability, and trustworthiness of the results are important concerns that should not be neglected in any kind of social research. Triangulation, which combines the use of different participants, methods, and data types, helps improve validity of the findings by enabling cross-verification of data obtained in a variety of ways. The use of thick description also ensures high quality data interpretation while the audit trail helps ensure dependability and accountability of the analysis process. Ethical aspects were also considered in the course of this research. Specifically, participation in the study was voluntary, while all respondents had been informed about the nature of the research project and had been assured that confidentiality of their identities would be guaranteed.

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4.0. RESULTS

The findings of the current study highlight a number of inconsistencies that characterize the Sondu border conflict situation: despite a high level of awareness of conflict management procedures and actors, there is low connectivity of the community with the institutional EWER system established by the National Policy on Peacebuilding and Conflict Management (2015). All the findings presented below consistently support this idea: in reality, communities are experiencing a fragmented system of conflict intervention rather than a formal, institutionalized policy-based warning approach to early warning and early response. This is a critical element for understanding the problem that this research addresses. Therefore, the core issue is not the absence of a warning and response system as such, but the low level of social embedment and institutional visibility of the formal EWER framework.

The findings concerning the awareness are particularly illustrative in terms of this argument. According to the survey results, 97.0% of respondents claimed that they are aware of the warning and response procedure. At the same time, only 5.1% recognized the formal CEWARN structure. By contrast, 60.0% believed that conflict management is conducted through chiefs and elders, and 25.4% through NGOs. Analytically, this finding is extremely important, since it shows that the actual warning system is much different from what the formal framework implies. Specifically, communities are aware of conflict prevention strategies in terms of those actors who are involved physically in response during escalation of the situation, not because of the formal architecture embedded in policies and other related frameworks. Therefore, the social aspect of EWER in Sondu does not relate to CEWARN. Another important finding in relation to this problem was revealed in the context of conflict reporting. The study showed that 43.2% of respondents report cases of conflict to chiefs, 30.3% – to elders, and 1.4% to peace committees (formal warning structures). These figures illustrate the fact that reporting of conflict is done along the lines of trust and accessibility, rather than according to the rules established by policies. Thus, chiefs and elders represent dominant figures due to their availability and immediate responsiveness during the time of crisis. In turn, peace committees and other formal EWER-related actors remain distant and invisible for ordinary community members. Indeed, qualitative narratives confirmed that "the first person you go to is the chief or elders," while local administrators also admitted that peace committees existed, but remained largely invisible for community members. The result is an institutional double structure of early warning, in which one type of warning operates socially, while another exists within policy framework but is not integrated into community activities.

The findings about the types of conflict incidents that communities experience within Sondu provide additional support to the main analytical conclusions made above. Specifically, respondents reported experiencing conflicts involving theft of livestock, rumors, political violence, hate speech, and armed confrontations simultaneously. This finding is particularly important in illustrating the complex nature of conflict, in which communication, economy, politics, and violence operate together in combination. Significantly, the role of rumors and hate speech as conflict signs is highly relevant. According to the data obtained in the process of interviews, initial tensions are often triggered by rumors, hate speech, or other communicative phenomena. This aspect is critical since it highlights the point that the initial signs of violence in the conflict situation are informal. At the same time, however, it can be assumed that the warning systems currently utilized in the area may not sufficiently be embedded into these processes and hence fail to respond to escalation signals timely.

The findings on the timeliness of response provide additional evidence to this problem. A combined percentage of 70.5% of respondents disagreed that the warning information was provided on time, while only 7.3% assessed it positively. Timeliness is a core aspect of any warning system, especially when it comes to preventive functions. According to the respondents, the process of reporting the warning occurs after the situation starts to escalate, and usually after violence is unleashed. Local administrative representatives confirmed this view and noted that although meetings, barazas, village informers' networks, patrols etc. exist, they are rarely conducted systematically, poorly coordinated, and restricted due to the lack of finance. Overall, what emerges from the findings is the fact that warning occurs in a fragmentary manner, which makes it difficult to conduct a structured institutional processing of information received from communities.

Weakness in timeliness of response inevitably translates into the analysis of trust and perception of the effectiveness of EWER systems. According to the data collected in the process of the survey, 70.0% of respondents distrust CEWARN systems, and 68.4% believe that formal warnings do not lead to concrete actions. Moreover, 85.2% of the respondents considered CEWARN framework, which constitutes a part of the formal NPPBCM 2015 policy, ineffective. This finding can be regarded as one of the most informative and analytical aspects of the research, showing that communities rely on concrete performance and not mere existence of certain institutions to assess warning systems. Consequently, trust is placed on chiefs, elders, churches, and NGO's as those actors who physically respond to escalation of the situation. By contrast, CEWARN is seen as remote, detached, and irrelevant in practice. This distrust, however, is not irrational, but rather based on accumulated experience of communities.

Findings about community participation and training also corroborate the above arguments. Despite community members active involvement in reporting and peace-building, only 19.2% of respondents viewed themselves participating in any formal EWER systems, and as high as 85.9% of respondents never received any training in connection with these processes. Analytically, these findings are critical for understanding that community participation occurs within the social domain and is not supported by formal

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institutions. Hence, individuals explained their actions by the fact that "we report issues," "we join discussions," or "work with elders." At the same time, administrative officials and community leaders (chiefs and NGOs), by contrast, had access to EWER training and knowledge. Therefore, the system has an unbalanced character, whereby EWER-related information remains concentrated in the hands of few officials, chiefs, or other peace actors, and is not adequately transferred to community members. Lastly, the findings on key challenges support the previous patterns outlined above. According to the survey results, 72.7% of respondents noted that the major obstacle to efficient functioning of EWER systems is lack of awareness, followed by political interference (46.8%), poor coordination (38.1%), and delayed response (37.8%). Lack of trust was reported by 33.8% of participants as well. Analytically, these findings show that all the weaknesses in EWER identified within the Sondu context are interrelated to each other: lack of awareness leads to non-participation, poor coordination prevents timely response, delayed response creates mistrust, etc. The significance of political factors within the current environment should be mentioned too: according to the interviewees, interventions often take place on political ground during elections period, and responses may be influenced by political interests of certain elites.

5.0. DISCUSSION

5.1. Re-reading the Sondu Conflict through Galtung's Conflict Triangle

The findings of this research require substantial reconsideration both of the Sondu border conflict and of how formal EWER systems function in a localized context. Many previous analyses of the Sondu/Kisumu–Kericho conflict have tended to look at it primarily in terms of well-known variables: ethnicity, political violence, land, cattle theft, resources, politics, and borders (Juma & Simiyu, 2019; KECOSCE, 2022; NCIC, 2022, 2023; Ombeck et al., 2019; Saferworld, 2015). These studies provide essential contributions insofar as they reveal the key actors, triggers, and events that have shaped the conflict over time. However, viewed in light of the present findings, they appear to fall short of providing an adequate analysis of conflict, since they tend to focus on visible and event-based instances of conflict without addressing how the conflict emerges through social imagination, narrative justification, political mobilization, and enactment. This is why Galtung's conflict triangle is highly applicable to reading the Sondu conflict not as a series of ethnic and border disputes, but as a multilayered conflict process in which different types of violence constantly intertwine (Galtung, 1969, 1990, 1996).

First of all, the present findings show that direct violence in Sondu is only the top layer of conflict that can occur after a prolonged period of structural and cultural violence. Attacks, cattle rustling, political violence, hate speech, and retaliation certainly matter. But they are only surface manifestations of deeper structural tensions within communities. As evidenced by the findings, rumours, fear, suspicion, and politically motivated narrative constructions play an important role in making communities feel insecure. In Galtungian terminology, rumours and hate speech can be regarded as instances of cultural violence insofar as they give meaning to hostile relations between people, transform suspiciousness into collective fears, and render retaliatory actions necessary for those who already live in an environment of mutual mistrust (Galtung, 1990). This finding adds an important dimension to the dominant literature on Sondu by indicating that ethnic clashes do not emerge out of nowhere. Communities have prepared themselves to clash because of how they think, speak, remember, interpret, and perceive each other even before they fight each other.

Secondly, the findings also show that structural violence in Sondu cannot be reduced to mere ethnic animosity between two ethnic groups. Ethnic tensions certainly contribute to conflict, but the latter has deep institutional, political, and economic roots that foster insecurity and mistrust among communities. While acknowledging the crucial role of land, cattle theft, boundary claims, political mobilization, and election as conflict drivers, previous analyses of Sondu are still inadequate in that they overlook the complex interplay of institutional, social, economic, and security conditions that make these factors conflict producing (Juma & Simiyu, 2019; Ombeck et al., 2019; Saferworld, 2015). As this study demonstrates, factors such as lack of institutional embedding, low levels of trust in local administrations, vulnerability of youth, economic insecurity, and fragmented local conflict governance contribute to conflicts between neighbouring communities. It is evident that in Sondu, formal institutions exist, but they are not yet deeply socially embedded. This means that while there is the state presence, it may not necessarily be the state presence that is needed by the local communities. Structural violence in this case means insufficient institutional protection from violent outcomes that affect communities.

This reading also helps understand why the findings challenge ethnicized readings that have frequently been presented in some scholarship and popular media reports on the Sondu conflict. Previous literature correctly identifies the ethnic character of Sondu, but it tends to present it oversimplifiedly. As this study demonstrates, communities in Sondu are not homogenous blocs, but complex social fields that involve ordinary residents, youths, elders, traders, chiefs, local administrators, politicians, churches, NGOs, and peace actors. Some of these actors contribute to the escalation of tensions, whereas others attempt to mediate the conflicts. Similarly, some of these actors profit from chaos, while others are its victims. Therefore, the ethnicization of Sondu may be seen as a misleading interpretation. Communities do not fight each other merely because of their ethnic differences. Instead, ethnic identities have been mobilized in Sondu by political motives, historical grievances, economic factors, and local networks of trust and distrust. In other

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words, this study brings a new perspective on the Sondu conflict by moving from ethnicized interpretation to conflict process analysis.

Finally, this Galtungian approach also explains why formal early warning systems seem inadequate in the context of the current findings. It is true that early warning systems tend to prioritize events associated with direct violence, such as cattle theft, attacks, hate speech, political violence, casualties, displacement, injuries, and destruction. But if we use the three-layered approach suggested by Galtung's model, then warning signs may come much sooner as structural and cultural manifestations of impending violence. Such signs include rumours, youth frustration, avoidance of public places, politically motivated speech, revival of past grievances, changes in the movement patterns, erosion of trust, and spread of fears through social networks. As shown by this study, local communities are able to detect these warning signs well ahead of formal early warning systems. And this is the second major drawback of formal EWER systems that are not adequately embedded within local social spaces. In this regard, the present study extends Galtung's model by suggesting a novel reading of EWER.

The same pattern can be applied to participation. It is established that communities participate actively in reporting, mediation, dialogue, and informal warning sharing, while only a small number considers itself as participants of EWER processes through formal structures. It means that there may be an existing phenomenon of disconnected participation – there is participation, yet it is underutilized within formal structures of early warning and response. This is relevant since formal systems require input of information from communities and its analysis and implementation. If such input remains mostly informal, personalized and disconnected from any institutional analysis and response, EWER systems will continue to function alongside communities, and not with their engagement. This finding revises the literature on participatory peacebuilding which claims that participation is meaningful by mere existence, but it can acquire meaning only when community activity is recognized and integrated into formal response mechanisms. Therefore, in Sondu, there is participation, although it is not systematized institutionally.

Another contribution to the literature comes from the study's findings regarding trust. Trust, according to these findings, is not an abstract feature. Instead, it is a combination of perception about actors' accessibility, responsiveness and performance. Communities trust chiefs and elders because of their nearness and responsiveness. On the contrary, they lack trust in formal systems due to their distance, low understanding, delay and invisibility. While supporting arguments of institutional trust literature that trust can be developed through responsiveness and reliability (Levi & Stoker, 2000), this research finds a special place for it in the context of conflict prevention. Specifically, in conflict settings, trust cannot be considered as a luxury variable. On the contrary, in conflict environments, it is one of the components of the warning mechanism. Individuals and groups communicate with whom they trust, and do not communicate with whom they consider unreliable. Therefore, weak trust leads to a weakening of EWER chain even at the stage of information gathering. From this perspective, this research makes a substantial contribution to EWER literature.

Training and exposure play an important role in this regard. The percentage of those who have never had exposure or training to formal EWER mechanisms (85.9%) explains the high degree of Sondu communities' unawareness of CEWARN. Training plays the crucial role of making policy comprehensible for communities. The lack of training implies that individuals cannot tell apart formal early warning mechanisms from other activities like chief's regular administration, NGO peace building meetings, church mediation and elder-led reconciliations. This substantially supports the main thesis of the paper that the limitation of formal EWER systems comes not from the rejection of communities, but their unawareness of them. The imbalance between administrators and citizens is especially clear – while chiefs, NGAO officers and peace activists understand EWER structures, ordinary citizens have no idea about them. This implies the creation of institutional hierarchy when system administrators understand the functioning of system better than its beneficiaries.

Moreover, this research brings back politics to EWER analysis. The finding that 46.8% of respondents mentioned political influence as a serious obstacle shows that peacebuilding cannot be perceived as a technically detached field. On the contrary, early warning system operates in a political environment, especially before the elections. Therefore, Sondu conflict environment may be characterized by youth mobilization, use of ethnical conflicts, selective response and elite interests. As Richmond (2011) and Mac Ginty (2014) argue in their criticism of the political economy of peacebuilding, institutional mechanisms do not function separately from political contexts and interests. However, this study suggests an additional insight: political influences not only create conditions for conflicts, but undermine confidence in conflict resolution systems. When citizens consider that any intervention would be late, influenced by politics or manipulated, they start losing faith in the whole warning-response structure. Political influences therefore are drivers as well as inhibitors of conflicts.

These findings help to reconsider Sondu conflict in the context of peace studies. The earlier research was absolutely right that ethnicity, cattle thefts, territorial issues, political violence and inter-border conflicts were the factors of Sondu. This research does not aim to discredit previous studies. Instead, it aims to provide them with a theoretical lens of analyzing these factors – Galtung's conflict triangle. Theft of livestock, physical confrontations, displacement and political attacks constitute direct violence. Weak institutional trust, competition for resources, poverty and irregular responsiveness of government agencies constitute structural violence. Ethnic tensions, rumors, hate speech and fears represent cultural violence. The most important finding is that formal

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EWER systems focus more on direct violence than its structural and cultural precursors. It explains their late response, poor visibility and weak effectiveness. Therefore, this research provides a new perspective on analyzing Sondu and EWER systems. What matters is not whether a warning system is able to predict a conflict, but what kind of conflict.

The key innovation lies in the fact that the research uses Galtung's model as the instrument of evaluating the effectiveness of the system, not only as the theoretical background. Using it, the researcher realizes that a warning system should be analyzed in terms of how it responds to three types of conflicts. Firstly, it needs to identify structural conditions: resource competition, institutional exclusion, insecure livelihood, vulnerability of youth and irregular responsiveness of institutions. Secondly, it needs to identify cultural signs of conflict: rumors, stereotypes, hate speech and moral justifications of retribution. And thirdly, it needs to take necessary measures before they turn into direct violence. The finding of this study demonstrates that current EWER systems have difficulties with the first two layers: they are better in detecting direct violence. As a result, response is too late, trust is weakened, and people prefer informal actors. Therefore, this research demonstrates that social embedding of the system is not a possible improvement, but a requirement for early warning.

The implication of the research for peacebuilding policy may be described as follows: CEWARN and its structures may be present, but presence does not equate effectiveness. Even having peace committees as parts of EWER architecture, we see that 1.4% of respondents report to them. This shows that their functional effectiveness remains low. Training may take place among certain individuals, but if 85.9% of people have no information on CEWARN, its social effectiveness is limited. Warning signals may come regularly, but if 70.5% of them are not in time and 68.4% of them do not lead to responses, EWER chain breaks up. In general, this research contributes to peacebuilding scholarship by emphasizing the social component of early warning systems and by changing the criteria of their assessment.

5.2. Formal Warning and Social Invisibility: Rethinking the EWER Literature in the Light of Sondu Evidence

One of the main conclusions drawn from the analysis of Sondu evidence is the fact that, although the institutional structure of warning systems exists, the social visibility of warning systems does not necessarily follow. The key point about this conclusion lies in the way the EWER system was perceived in the case in question. Indeed, the literature on early warning has traditionally focused on the organizational and technological aspects of prevention: information gathering, analysis, risk assessment, communication channels and preventive response systems (Austin, 2004; Lund, 2009; Nyheim, 2009; Schmeidl & Jenkins, 1998; Wulf & Debiel, 2009). The mentioned scholarship has proved extremely valuable for the development of the theory of preventive governance and shown the fact that many forms of violent conflict develop following observable stages. Nevertheless, if analyzed from the point of view of the Sondu case, the existing literature seems to make a crucial assumption about early warning systems. Namely, it implies that once institutional structures are established and operationalized, warning signs will automatically become socially visible. The findings of the research in question refute the assumption radically.

According to the findings, institutional visibility does not mean social visibility. Although communities were fully aware of the presence of peace actors, conflict management, meetings, mediations and other processes taking place locally, 94.9% of respondents did not see CEWARN as the formalized mechanism behind them. Nevertheless, 97.0% were conscious of the existence of some kind of warning or management. In that context, the contradiction becomes particularly important because it suggests that a warning system may operate in the administrative context even without being socially visible for local populations. What they recognize is not the policy but the actors involved in the policy and experience gained through this interaction. Thus, chiefs, elders, churches, traders' networks, youth leaders and NGOs become the visible representatives of conflict management because they are physically close and present in the areas where local people interact on the daily basis. As a consequence, institutional mechanisms of conflict management tend to remain remote, abstract and undifferentiated from other forms of administrative or humanitarian assistance.

This finding provides one of the most important directions in which early warning literature should evolve further. Indeed, Lund (2009) is right in emphasizing that the success of preventive measures depends on the ability of warning mechanisms to lead to response. The Sondu case, however, demonstrates that there is a step prior to response. In particular, communities become engaged in a warning system not because it exists institutionally but because they recognize and interpret it as the part of their social context. As a result, the problem identified by Wulf & Debiel (2009) starts before any formal response is necessary. It starts with the lack of social recognition and legibility of formal systems. In Sondu, the warning signs become obvious to communities well before any violence takes place as a consequence of rumours, discussions at the markets and political gatherings, relations among youth, funeral meetings, drinking parties, religious assemblies, cross border social interactions. Nevertheless, although warning circulates, this circulation does not always intersect formal mechanisms.

This fragmentation becomes clearly visible from other findings of the study. Conflict reporting is done through familiar and trusted channels rather than strictly according to the formal mechanisms set up in policies. Chiefs and elders take the largest share of information received in communities precisely because they are socially close, trustworthy and recognizable. On the contrary, peace committees and organizations affiliated to CEWARN play only a minor role in terms of social perception despite their central position in official mechanisms. This fact identifies another paradoxical element in many institutional warning systems: although

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these systems tend to be purely institutional, conflicts themselves usually operate socially before becoming institutional. Once recognized officially, these conflicts may emerge after communities experience weeks or even months of rumors, fear, political incitement and growing tension among members of various social groups.

At the same time, the findings of the current paper call for a reassessment of certain assumptions made in contemporary technological discourse in early warning literature. More specifically, recent studies devoted to EWER tend to pay a lot of attention to digital technologies, ICTs, mobile communications, social media and information systems aimed at quick and reliable transmission of information (Nyheim, 2009; Wulf & Debiel, 2009). While the current findings partly validate such optimism, they also highlight the limits of the approach. Technological innovations allow information to be spread quickly enough. Nevertheless, reaction to the warning remains delayed, fragmented and problematic. The community respondents emphasized the fact that warnings without appropriate response become annoying and do not contribute to any improvement. Consequently, in the contemporary world, technologies tend to improve the speed of communication while failing to address institutional problems related to coordination, political neutrality, legitimacy and operation.

This point, in its turn, suggests a need to review the idea of warning knowledge used in the current EWER policies. Indeed, according to much of literature dedicated to formal warning mechanisms, the indicators used for identifying potential warning are statistics on violence, displacement, number of incidents or hate speech. All those factors are important, of course, yet the Sondu case demonstrates the fact that communities tend to recognize escalating tensions long before statistics become visible. In particular, many respondents explained that warning occurs due to strange silence on the markets, unusual movement of people, rumors spreading fast, changed social relations, avoided markets, political talks, youth gatherings, etc. All those signs are not purely statistical but involve interpretive work of communities. Therefore, preventive systems should involve not just data gathering but listening carefully to communities themselves.

In that context, the current research provides a valuable contribution to early warning literature in the sense that it shows that communities are not passive consumers of information but active generators of warning signs. The latter point can be understood even better if we apply Galtung's conflict triangle. Institutional structures prove quite efficient in terms of recognizing direct violence that becomes visible, identifiable and measurable. On the contrary, structural and cultural violence tend to circulate socially before becoming institutionalized. The former is evident in terms of exclusion, distrust, uneven state responsiveness, economic and livelihood insecurity, institutional marginalization. The latter manifests itself through rumours, stereotypes, fear, narratives of betrayal, ethnic suspicion and historical background. Those factors also operate socially and are recognized better by communities than by official institutions. Thus, the main contribution of the research can be stated in the following manner: warning becomes preventive when able to detect the mentioned phenomena.

Moreover, the current findings also help to rethink the concept of EWER as a purely institutional tool independent of the political reality. Political interference emerged as one of the key threats to the efficiency of warning systems in Sondu. The respondents noted that the mentioned phenomenon occurred when interventions became selective, politically motivated, delayed or election-related. Such finding correlates with the ideas suggested by critical peacebuilding literature. According to scholars like Mac Ginty (2014), Richmond (2011), it is impossible to understand and analyze institutions without considering the political environment surrounding them. Yet the current findings make the analysis more specific. Political influence becomes a threat to both response efficiency and social acceptance of early warning mechanisms. Therefore, political interference becomes a reason of weakening the warning chain.

Finally, the findings on the training and awareness of respondents seem to be equally valuable in the light of the above considerations. Indeed, the main reason of institutional invisibility discussed in the current paper lies in the fact that people at the community level had practically no contact with CEWARN frameworks. The role of training is to ensure social awareness. If communities receive no education on the principles of the system, it will remain invisible. Hence, institutional initiatives aimed at implementation without providing the communities with the required information appear to be inefficient. The interviewees noted that administrators, NGAO officers and peace actors in general tended to know about formal mechanisms better than ordinary residents of Sondu. The difference led to the emergence of what could be called a verticalized warning architecture in the area.

In addition, verticalization explains to a great extent the discrepancy between participation and integration. Communities participate actively in reporting, mediating and implementing peacebuilding actions. Nevertheless, they do not view themselves as participants of an EWER system. This finding means that, although they participate actively, communities still do not operate within institutionalized frameworks of warning and response. In other words, community involvement does not necessarily equal participation. The current research expands participatory peacebuilding literature to a considerable extent by proving this important point.

Consequently, the current findings make it possible to conclude that existing literature on early warning should be supplemented by the focus on social aspects of warning processes. It is true that the existing works emphasize important aspects of warning such as coordination, innovations, information systems and response mechanisms. Nevertheless, according to the current findings, these

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features prove insufficient until institutional mechanisms become socially recognized. Hence, the major implication of the Sondu case can be formulated as follows: warning systems tend to fail not only when institutions fall apart but also when institutions prove socially distant from the local communities.

5.0. CONCLUSION

Overall, the findings of this study reveal that the challenge for Early Warning and Early Response systems in cases of repeated intra-state conflict like Sondu does not arise from a lack of institutionality, information, or peace actors but from a lack of social embedding in the contexts where violence occurs. Through a re-read of the Sondu border conflict using the framework of Galtung's conflict triangle, the research has established that while physical violence may occur in the form of border clashes, livestock raids, electoral violence, and counter-violence in response to such acts, this physical violence is itself generated by underlying socio-cultural factors of structural violence such as distrust, manipulation, livelihood insecurity, rumors, ethnicized rhetoric, historical grievances, and ineffective local governance arrangements. The study thus breaks away from dominant event-focused accounts, which have traditionally approached the Sondu border conflict as arising either from issues of ethnicity or electoral volatility (Juma & Simiyu, 2019; Ombeck et al., 2019; Saferworld, 2015). To this effect, the research has established that there is a significant relationship between the structure of the conflict and the history of conflict, indicating that the conflict emerges out of a relationality and historicity long before actual physical violence takes place. This study thus establishes the need for early warning systems able to read structural and cultural violence before the emergence of direct violence. The Sondu experience shows that while communities have substantial experiential knowledge for recognizing signs of warning, formal CEWARM frameworks are only partially integrated into social spaces where warnings first appear, hence creating a system that is administrative rather than social.

Moreover, this study makes a valuable contribution to peace and conflict research by reconceptualizing the warning–response gap in light of both institutional delays and issues of social embeddedness and recognizability. Current EWER research has mostly focused on institutional and technical aspects such as coordination, technology, information systems, and rapid responses (Lund, 2009; Nyheim, 2009; Wulf & Debiel, 2009); however, the Sondu experience indicates that the ability to effectively prevent conflict relies on the recognition of formal systems as legitimate, relevant, accessible, and meaningful within the daily experience of insecurity. In this context, chiefs, elders, churches, traders, youth, and NGOs dominate the conflict management arena not because of a lack of institutional frameworks, but because these social groups are recognized and trusted within the conflict interpretation process whereas formal institutions still fail to establish similar recognition. As a result, this study offers two critical contributions to theory and policy. First, the study shows that early warning systems become preventive only when they are socially embedded into relational spaces within which conflict is understood, talked about, and experienced. Second, without social embeddedness, formal early warning systems tend to remain reactive, responding only after the physical manifestations of violence arise from structural and cultural processes that have long preceded them.

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